

Situational Awareness Toward Natural Disasters at Regional Airports: A Qualitative Study of Employee Awareness and Coordination

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Article Info	Abstract
RESEARCH ARTICLE	Natural disasters are among the events that directly affect the social, economic and physical structure of societies, the frequency and impact of which is increasing. In this process, transportation infrastructures play a critical role in maintaining post-disaster response and recovery activities. Especially in cases where land transportation is damaged, airports become important centers for the dispatch of search and rescue teams, the delivery of humanitarian aid materials and the execution of evacuation operations. The aim of this study is to examine the awareness levels of employees working at a regional airport towards natural disasters, their experiences regarding disaster management, and their perceptions of disaster preparedness processes. Qualitative research method was adopted in the research and semi-structured interviews were used as data collection tools. The data obtained from volunteer participants working at a regional airport were evaluated using MAXQDA software with the thematic analysis method.
Keywords: Regional airports Disaster preparedness Qualitative research	The research findings show that the participants are generally aware of the current disaster and emergency plans and consider training and drill activities as important components of disaster preparedness. However, differences in employees' plan awareness levels reveal the importance of continuity of training and awareness activities. In addition, participant testimonies show that communication and coordination play a critical role in possible disaster situations. The findings show that disaster management is not only a response process. It reveals that it is perceived as a multifaceted phenomenon that includes the dimensions of preparation, education, awareness, communication and coordination. In conclusion, the study shows that employee awareness, training activities, and coordination practices are important elements in strengthening disaster preparedness at regional airports. The findings are expected to contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable disaster preparedness approaches for regional airports.
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1. Introduction

Natural disasters are among the main risks affecting both the physical environment and the social and economic structure around the world. Turkey, on the other hand, is frequently exposed to different types of disasters such as earthquakes, floods and landslides due to its geological and climatic characteristics (Ergünay, 2007). Floods

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and landslides, in particular, are not only the result of natural processes, but can become more destructive due to improper land use and human activities (Özcan, 2006; Öztürk, 2002). These disasters cause serious damage to transportation and infrastructure systems, complicating response processes. Therefore, the level of preparedness for disasters and crisis management capacity of airports, which are among the critical infrastructures, is of great importance.

After a disaster, air transportation comes to the fore in terms of delivering the needed logistics materials quickly. Therefore, airports play a critical role in delivering search and rescue teams, medical personnel, and humanitarian aid materials to the disaster area. In the international literature, it is stated that airports are the center of post-disaster logistics operations and especially air cargo transportation stands out as the fastest and most effective solution. The Get Airports Ready for Disaster (GARD) program developed in this context offers an international model that aims to increase the disaster preparedness levels of airports (DHL and UNDP, 2012). Airports should be evaluated in terms of passenger, cargo and general aviation activities in the pre-disaster period, their current capacities should be analyzed realistically, and applicable plans should be developed for possible disaster scenarios (Koçak & Yavuz, 2012). In addition, international regulatory organizations emphasize that airport emergency plans should be prepared with the participation of all stakeholders and updated regularly (FAA, 2009; ICAO, Annex 14). On the other hand, it should be taken into account that airport infrastructure may be damaged during natural disasters. In this context, the creation of action plans for the recommissioning of damaged facilities is expressed as a priority requirement for businesses (Bayazitoğlu & Güngör, 2023). It is known that transportation infrastructure can be seriously damaged and logistics activities can be disrupted to a great extent in times of disaster. In such crisis environments, humanitarian aid operations are conducted under logistical uncertainties, and effective supply chain management is critical (Pettit & Beresford, 2009). It is of great importance to deploy alternative transportation solutions and provide rapid access to disaster areas. Airports, on the other hand, are considered as an important logistical support and coordination point in disaster management processes thanks to their infrastructure and operational capacities.

The success of disaster management is not only with the resilience of physical infrastructure. It is also directly related to planning processes, organizational coordination and implementation capacity due to the human factor (Perry, 2007). The competence of the personnel working in disaster situations, the coordination capacity between units and the effectiveness of organizational decision processes play a decisive role in ensuring operational continuity in crisis conditions (Van Wassenhove, 2006). In this context, it is important to prepare disaster management plans, carry out regular drills and increase the disaster awareness of employees.

Studies on disaster management and airports mostly focus on the post-disaster operational capacity, infrastructure adequacy and inter-institutional coordination role of airports. As a matter of fact, Smith (2010) emphasized that regional cooperation, coordination and communication between airports during disasters are important for the continuity of operations. Ataseven et al. (2025) evaluated the earthquake preparedness of airports located on fault lines in Türkiye with multi-criteria decision-making methods. However, it is seen that regional airports should be evaluated not only in terms of passenger numbers or economic output, but also in terms of crisis management, local response capacity and social resilience. Große et al. (2021) stated that regional airports play critical roles in terms of crisis preparedness, civil defense and social resilience, using the example of Sweden. On the other hand, he stated that this role is often not visible enough. In this context, it can be said that while the existing literature focuses more on the infrastructure, capacity and coordination dimensions, the evaluations of employees working at regional airports regarding disaster perception, experiences and disaster preparedness processes are more limited. This highlights the need for studies focusing on the human factor at regional airports, as assessments of employee perceptions and disaster awareness are relatively limited. In this direction, the study aims to contribute to the literature with a qualitative perspective that focuses on the human factor.

The Western Black Sea Region is exposed to various natural disaster risks, particularly floods and excessive rainfall, due to its geographical and climatic characteristics. As an important transportation alternative for the region, airports play an important role in terms of search and rescue and humanitarian aid activities in terms of uninterrupted service in times of disaster. In this context, a regional airport in the Western Black Sea Region was evaluated as a suitable research environment in terms of examining the disaster awareness of its employees,

their experiences regarding disasters and their perceptions of disaster preparedness processes. This study aims to examine the awareness of employees working at a regional airport towards natural disasters, their experiences regarding disaster preparedness processes and their perceptions of these processes.

Fig. 1: Keyword co-occurrence network of airport-related disaster and crisis management studies.

Figure 1 presents a keyword co-occurrence network created using VOSviewer. The distribution of keywords suggests that airport-related disaster and crisis management studies have primarily focused on themes such as operational disruption, resilience, emergency response, coordination and planning. Recent reviews also indicate that shock events affecting airports are commonly examined through their impacts on air travel demand, airport operations, operating procedures, facilities and infrastructure (Gu et al., 2024).

The presence of terms such as airport capacity, coordination, airport governance and environmental risks may therefore be interpreted as an indication that airport risk management is discussed not only as a technical issue, but also as an operational and organizational problem. In this respect, studies on airport surge capacity emphasize the importance of staff, space, supplies, systems, communication and capacity planning during disaster conditions (Polater, 2020). At the same time, regional airports deserve separate attention. Research on regional airports in Sweden indicates that these airports play an important role in crisis preparedness, emergency response and societal resilience, particularly in remote or sparsely populated areas (Große et al., 2021). Therefore, examining the perceptions of employees at regional airports regarding disaster preparedness, communication and coordination practices may make a more local and human-oriented contribution to the current debate in the literature.

Fig. 2: Workflow of the research.

Rather than focusing solely on technical and managerial aspects, the research centers on the perspectives of employees with direct field experience. In this context, the process is designed as a qualitative case study. Employees’ awareness regarding disaster preparedness, perceptions of response processes, training and exercise experiences, and communication and coordination practices were discussed. The general workflow of the research and the stages followed are given in Figure 2.

2. Conceptual Framework

The main feature of structured interviews is that the questions to be asked to the participants are presented in a predetermined and standardized order. In these interviews, answer options can be predefined or open-ended questions can be posed to the interviewer, providing limited flexibility. Due to its standardized structure, structured interviews are considered as one of the closest methods to the quantitative research approach among qualitative data collection techniques. Structured interviews are generally preferred when it is desired to obtain comparable and standardized data from larger sample groups. Presenting questions in a predetermined pattern allows for the collection of similar types of data from different participants. In addition, it is stated that in studies involving more than one interviewer, it contributes to obtaining more consistent data as it reduces the differences in the interview process (Opdenakker, 2006). In addition, the ability to re-apply structured interviews at regular intervals facilitates data comparison in longitudinal studies (Bryman, 2016).

In qualitative research, it may not always be possible to establish direct causal relationships between events and facts. However, situations that are difficult to measure with quantitative methods can be revealed through more in-depth examinations. Qualitative research focuses on examining individuals' experiences, perceptions, and the meanings they attribute to events within their natural context. For this reason, an interpretive and understanding approach comes to the fore in qualitative research rather than a deterministic approach (Karataş, 2015). Qualitative research is based on participant experiences, observations, interviews, and text-based analysis rather than numerical data. Through data collection techniques such as interviews, observations and document analysis, a deeper understanding of the subject under investigation is tried to be obtained (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008; Karataş, 2015). The researcher's observations, participant statements, and discourse analyses contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Gülcan, 2025). In this respect, qualitative research offers an important approach to making sense of individuals' thoughts, experiences and social realities (Berg, 2001). Qualitative research also takes into account the natural context in which events and phenomena take place and allows the researcher to evaluate these phenomena within the framework of the participants' opinions, experiences and interpretations. In this direction, qualitative research focuses not only on results but also on how processes develop and are experienced by individuals (Özdemir & Şahinöz, 2022; Ulaş, 2025). In the process of designing and conducting qualitative research, researchers have a more flexible and dynamic field of study. Qualitative research focuses on the phenomenon to be discovered and tries to understand individuals' perceptions, experiences and thoughts about events and phenomena in their natural environment (Turhan, 2023). The researcher's ability to develop new questions during the data collection process and to direct the research process in line with the data obtained are among the important features of qualitative research. This flexible structure provides significant advantages, especially in researching topics that have been previously studied at a limited level.

In this study, semi-structured interview technique was preferred as the data collection method. Semi-structured interviews are a data collection method that is based on a predetermined interview form and provides flexibility to the researcher in the interview process. While proceeding within the framework of certain questions, the researcher can ask alternative questions and examine the subject more deeply depending on the answers given by the participants (Özmen, 2023). This method allows participants to present their experiences, perceptions and evaluations in a more natural and detailed way in their own words. Additionally, it is often preferred in qualitative research in the field of social sciences as it is an effective method for understanding human experiences and individual perspectives (Ertaş & Atalay, 2023).

3. Methodology

The data collection process within the scope of the research is based on semi-structured interviews with the personnel working at a regional airport. This method was chosen to examine in detail the perceptions and experiences of airport personnel regarding disaster preparedness, response processes in disaster situations, training practices and coordination experiences. Thus, not only the answers given by the participants to certain questions, but also their own perspectives, suggestions and evaluations based on their experiences were included in the analysis process. Open-ended questions asked in the interviews; It focuses on disaster

preparedness practices, applicability and awareness of crisis and emergency plans, response processes carried out in the event of a disaster, adequacy of training and exercise activities, and communication and coordination practices between units. In addition, the suggestions of the participants for the development of disaster awareness and preparedness processes were also evaluated.

In the recording of the data, the semi-structured interview transcript was used in a thematic structure for the purposes of the study. Through this form, not only participant expressions, but also non-verbal elements observed during the interview process (emphasis, intonation, hesitation, confidence level, etc.) were recorded by note-taking. Thus, it is aimed to protect data integrity. After all interviews were completed, the data obtained were transferred to the digital environment and made ready for analysis.

In the data analysis process, a qualitative analysis approach was adopted and MAXQDA software was used. In the first stage, open coding was applied and meaningful data pieces were generated from participant statements. These codes represent commonalities and recurring thought patterns that stand out in participant responses. The codes obtained were then grouped according to their similar contents and collected under subcategories, and this structure was organized within the framework of higher level categories and main themes. Accordingly, the analysis process is designed according to the hierarchy of main theme, category, subcategory (code). Figure 3 summarizes the methodological process of the research, including data collection, preparation, and analysis.

Fig. 3: Methodological workflow of the research.

Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants before the interviews. Ethical principles and confidentiality requirements were considered throughout the research process. Within the scope of the research, interviews were conducted with a total of 6 participants. In addition, the data obtained from the direct participant statements were preserved in the analysis process, ensuring that the comments were data-based. During the analysis process, coding processes were reviewed and coding consistency was tried to be strengthened in order to increase the reliability of the findings.

4. Results and Discussions

The findings obtained as a result of the qualitative analysis are structured under the main theme of disaster management and awareness. Within the scope of this main theme, six basic categories have been determined: Enhancement of Disaster Management Capacity, Inter-Unit Coordination, Training and Drill Experiences, Crisis Plan Awareness and Competence, Institutional Response in Disaster Situations and Institutional Disaster Preparedness Level. The thematic structure obtained as a result of the analysis is presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: The thematic framework of disaster management and awareness based on qualitative analysis.

When the thematic structure is examined, it is seen that disaster management is not limited to response activities in times of crisis. It is seen that it is handled within the framework of interrelated dimensions such as preparation, communication, coordination, education and awareness. These categories reflect employees' perceptions and evaluations of disaster preparedness and response processes rather than an objective evaluation of organizational performance. The findings show that the participants consider disaster management as a multidimensional process shaped by preparedness, awareness, communication and coordination practices.

Code System	K1_D...	K2_D...	K3_D...	K4_D...	K5_D...	K6_D...
Disaster Management and Awareness						
Enhancement of Disaster Management Capacity						
Sufficient capacity	•	•		•		•
Infrastructure improvement suggestion					•	
Inter-Unit Coordination						
Communication infrastructure		•				
No coordination problems	•			•		•
Continuity of communication				•	•	•
Training and Drill Experiences						
Drill participation		•	•			
Adequate and regular training	•	•		•	•	•
Crisis Plan Awareness and Competence						
Task awareness		•				
Confidence in implementation						•
High plan awareness	•			•	•	•
Institutional Response in Disaster Situations						
Institutional support	•				•	•
Previous disaster experience	•					•
Strong response reflex		•		•		•
Institutional Disaster Preparedness Level						
Guidance from higher authorities			•			
Willingness to take expanded roles			•			
Operational safety			•			
External institutional coordination				•	•	
Participation in training and drills	•					
Active participation	•	•		•		

Fig. 5: Distribution of key codes across participants.

When the code distributions in Figure 5 are examined, it is seen that some codes are expressed jointly by more than one participant. It is especially noteworthy that codes such as sufficient capacity, adequate and regular

communication and coordination play an important role in possible disaster situations. In general, the findings show that disaster management is not only about written plans and procedures; It reveals that it is considered as a multidimensional process shaped by preparation, training, communication, coordination and employee participation. In this respect, employee experiences and perceptions provide important information for understanding disaster preparedness processes at regional airports.

In line with the research findings, it is recommended that disaster preparedness activities carried out at regional airports should be regularly reviewed and supported by continuous training and awareness programs. It is important to adapt the disaster scenarios used in training and exercises to local conditions, taking into account the geographical and climatic characteristics of different regions. In addition, it is recommended to continuously strengthen communication and coordination practices in order to increase the preparedness levels of employees for possible disaster situations. The findings show that disaster preparedness processes should be handled not only within the framework of plans and procedures, but also within the scope of human factors such as employee awareness, communication, coordination and active participation. Accordingly, it is envisaged that encouraging more participation of employees in training and preparedness activities can contribute to increasing disaster awareness.

One of the important limitations of the research is the limited number of participants. It is thought that the studies to be carried out with larger participant groups and at different regional airports in the future will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of disaster awareness and preparedness processes in the aviation industry.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the Kastamonu University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee (Meeting No: 6; Decision No: 7; Date: 21.05.2025).

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